

IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES ON THE ECONOMICS

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ANNOTATION: The change of generations of computing technology is equivalent to another scientific and technological revolution. With the advent of new generations of computers, communication facilities, multiprocessor systems and the development of Internet technologies, it will be possible not only to solve fundamentally new problems in all areas of science and technology, but also to significantly expand the possibilities for their implementation. Solving previously traditional problems at a new, qualitative level, the qualitative level of solving problems, first of all, involves providing the necessary and sufficient intellectual support[1]. This study employs the IMRAD method to investigate the current state of AI in higher education, its economic implications, and future prospects. The findings suggest that AI can enhance teaching and learning experiences, streamline administrative processes, and open up new revenue streams for universities[2]. However, the adoption of AI also presents challenges, such as the need for significant investments in infrastructure and the potential for job displacement. The article concludes with recommendations for universities and policymakers to harness the benefits of AI while mitigating its risks. Intellectualization of information and computing systems means not only the use of new-generation tools, but also the use of a new generation of mathematical, algorithmic and software tools. Information and computing systems with intellectual support are usually used to solve complex problems where logical information processing is superior to computational processing. Examples of such problems are: understanding and synthesizing texts in natural language, understanding and synthesizing speech, analyzing visual information, controlling robots, analyzing situations and making decisions.

KEYWORDS: Artificial intelligence, management information systems, Higher Education, database, Ethical AI Implementation, development of yield assessment program, Risk management, Personalized Learning, Automation, Job Displacement

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are becoming the main tools for generating and evaluating data on the Internet. If implemented responsibly, AI can benefit society in many ways. However, there is also a risk that such technologies will have a negative impact on fundamental freedoms. The use of artificial intelligence for commercial, political or state interests can seriously threaten human rights, especially freedom of expression and media pluralism. The problem of AI governance is an issue in the field of artificial intelligence technology and philosophy[3]. The goal is to create artificial superintelligence that benefits people, while avoiding the accidental creation of intelligence that causes harm. It is especially important to avoid a situation where AI takes over control and makes it impossible to switch off[4]. The results of research on AI governance can also be applied to the governance of existing AI systems.

MATERIALS

Activities related to the implementation of modern computing technology require significant material and labor costs. A prerequisite for the use of these tools is to achieve economic efficiency from their implementation. This requires calculating the economic efficiency and justifying it. Justifying the economic efficiency of using information technologies allows you to:

- determine the need and feasibility of costs for creating and implementing an automated system for collecting and processing information at various levels of the EIS;
- establish the main directions of automation of information processing based on the specifics of various levels of the EIS, as well as the methods of receiving, transmitting and processing information at each of them;
- select economically efficient options for technological processes for processing economic information.

The economic efficiency of automated information processing is ensured by the following main factors:

- high speed of operations for collecting, transmitting, processing and issuing information, achieved due to the high productivity of modern technical means, maximum reduction in the time required to perform individual operations;
- improving the quality of economic calculations due to the creation of a single information base, establishing a clear schedule for its receipt, eliminating constant data and derivative indicators from it, as well as due to its centralized processing;
- improving information services for various levels of the EIS due to the reduction in the time required to develop and receivedocuments.

Based on the above, it should be said that the overall efficiency of using information technologies is directly dependent on the reduction in the costs of information processing (the so-called direct efficiency) and on the achieved increase in the level of information services (the so-called indirect efficiency) [5].

Direct efficiency is expressed in the reduction of labor and cost costs for processing economic information and directly, i.e. quantitatively, affects the economic performance of computing installations engaged in its processing.

Indirect efficiency characterizes the qualitative changes that occur as a result of the use of computing equipment. They are expressed in the improvement of the quality of economic calculations, the increase in the composition of the information received, the increase in its reliability and efficiency, etc.

It should be said that at present there are difficulties in calculating indirect efficiency, since there are no methods for assessing the share of efficiency from machine processing of information in the overall efficiency obtained as a result of various measures to improve information services of economic entities.

In this case, it is recommended to use the method of expert assessments to calculate the expected indirect efficiency. It consists in the fact that, based on the analysis of changes in the system of processing economic information for several periods, its possible improvement as a result of using more operational and analytical information is determined by expert means.

Direct economic efficiency indicators are determined as a result of comparing the costs of processing information of several design solution options. It is important that they are considered under equal conditions, i.e. with the coincidence of the composition of the tasks to be solved, the volume of initial data, and the degree of reliability.

In a simplified approach, this is a comparison of two options - the designed and the basic. The existing technology of automated processing of economic information is taken as the basic option, and the designed option is the result of modification of the existing technology. The absolute indicator of the economic efficiency of the project being developed is the reduction in annual cost and labor costs for information processing compared to the basic version of the technological process of information processing or the method of solving the problem.

METHODS

Information technology plays a huge role in the modern economy. Very often we can hear such a concept as virtual or information economy. This is due to the fact that information technology and economics are two related areas that together provide a positive economic effect and a positive production result. Without the latest information technology, the economy cannot develop normally, and the state will end up on the list of laggards[4]. Information technology is a process that consists of rules for performing operations and actions performed on

data. The main goal of information technology is to obtain the information the user needs by performing actions to process primary data. Information technology in economics is a set of actions that are performed on economic information using computers and other equipment in order to obtain a positive optimal result. In economics, information technology is needed for efficient processing, sorting and selection of data in order to implement the most efficient process of interaction between humans and computing equipment in order to meet the need for information, as well as to implement operational interaction. The use of technology in economics is a means of virtual economics. The virtual economy is an environment or a special economic space where electronic business is carried out, in other words, an economy based on the use of interactive capabilities. Electronic business is a company's activity aimed at making a profit and based on technologies and their advantages. Electronic business includes various information technologies:

Technologies in electronic commerce are one of the ways to carry out electronic business. Therefore, electronic commerce contains a number of technologies[5]:

- electronic data interchange protocol;
- e-mail;

Internet. Of these components, the most developed will be considered the electronic data interchange protocol - this is a way of assigning codes to operations and processing them online.

Speaking about the commercial side of the Internet's capabilities, the structure of electronic commerce looks like this:

- electronic data interchange protocol;
- e-mail;

Internet. Of these components, the most developed will be considered the electronic data interchange protocol - this is a way of assigning codes to transactions, and their processing in on-line mode.

Speaking about the commercial side of the Internet, the structure of e-commerce looks like this:

- customer relations;
- advertising;
- buying and selling via the Internet - this is the essence of electronic commerce;
- services.

Electronic auction technologies. It is through electronic auctions that trading activities take place on electronic trading platforms with the aim of bringing together sellers and buyers. The sources of income received from electronic auctions are commissions for transactions carried out and advertising.

Electronic banks. This activity involves two forms: electronic banks and traditional banks operating online. Electronic banks make services more accessible

to customers, use a 24-hour mode of operation. Since such banks provide a wide range of services for their customers, as a result of the use of process automation, they fully use electronic capabilities[6].

RESULTS

Electronic signage technologies. With their help, customers can now search for goods and services on the Internet. Electronic mail. This is a postal service where messages are delivered using electronic methods. Electronic brokerage services - are carried out in the financial market, which provide agreements between sellers and buyers. Nowadays, information is one of the most important resources for the development of society along with material and human resources. With the help of information products and services, society is able to satisfy the needs for new information and knowledge, as well as various aesthetic needs. The main function of information products is to provide certain information and means that can recreate this knowledge.

Information technologies are understood as a set of methods using information laws, models and processes of production of means and methods of information processing . Recently, within the framework of the scientific direction of artificial intelligence, the concept of "modern information technologies" has appeared, which includes: knowledge engineering, fuzzy data processing, soft computing, neural network technologies, evolutionary modeling (genetic algorithms), multi-agent systems. The listed technologies implement not only new models of knowledge representation, but also modern heuristic algorithms for obtaining approximate solutions that cannot be found an exact solution or require a lot of work. Intelligent information technologies are a means of developing intelligent information systems, which has recently become a very common commercial product, in great demand among users in various fields of activity. Examples of such systems are expert systems, intelligent control systems, intelligent databases, cognitive graphic systems, self-learning systems, flexible information systems. Most of the listed systems can be implemented as fuzzy systems that use a linguistic model to represent information, and problem solving, a special case of knowledge-based inference, is based on logical inference.

The Master's programme in Fundamental Computer Science and Intelligent Information Technologies includes the study of the following subjects: Knowledge engineering and knowledge base design (characteristics of knowledge as a special type of information, strategies for working with knowledge, knowledge representation models: logic, framework, network), production, formalization of linguistic logical inference, methods of forming a knowledge base for production systems, parametric and structural optimization of knowledge bases), processing of uncertain data (uncertainty factor and methods of its formalization; the concept of a fuzzy set and related definitions; fuzzy numbers and); Fuzzy modeling in MatLab

and focused on linguistic information, intelligent information systems and technologies for their development (modern information technologies providing intelligent functions); main classes of intelligent information systems: expert systems, intelligent interface systems, self-learning and adaptive systems; design features of intelligent information systems; technologies and development tools), decision support systems (the main stages of the decision-making process; multi-criteria decision-making model and the Pareto principle; multi-criteria structural analysis; decision-making under uncertainty and risk; linguistic approach to decision-making). - architecture of decision support systems, features of information presentation and development), modern heuristic algorithms (ideas of modern algorithms; basic concepts of evolutionary modeling; genetic algorithms and genetic programming; ant algorithms; cellular automata and DNA computing; areas of application of technologies). and possible modifications), Intelligent data analysis (the main tasks of data analysis; problems of recognition and pattern recognition; methods of logical recognition; fuzzy classification; fuzzy regression analysis; trend detection; models; evaluate multidimensional objects for data analysis); The areas of professional activity of graduates studying under the Master's program "Intelligent Information Technologies" are IT industry enterprises, as well as enterprises and organizations using IT systems, products and services in their activities.

Improving operational efficiency is an important goal for organizations looking to optimize performance and drive growth. Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into management information systems (MIS) is a powerful strategy to achieve this goal. An AI-enabled MIS automates repetitive tasks, streamlines processes, and provides real-time insights that improve efficiency and cost effectiveness. Using machine learning algorithms, an AI-powered MIS can analyze large volumes of data to identify patterns, trends, and opportunities for optimization. Predictive analytics capabilities allow organizations to anticipate future needs, allocate resources efficiently, and minimize risks. Additionally, an AI-integrated MIS improves collaboration and facilitates decision making by providing centralized access to data and insights across departments. Overall, integrating AI into a MIS allows organizations to operate more efficiently, respond more effectively to market changes, and ultimately gain a competitive advantage in today's dynamic business environment.

DISCUSSION

The inclusion of artificial intelligence (AI) in management information systems (MIS) raises important ethical issues that require careful consideration. First, data privacy and security must be maintained to ensure that sensitive data is protected from unauthorized access and potential misuse. Organizations must

implement strict measures, such as encryption and access control, to protect people's privacy.

Second, it is important to ensure that AI algorithms are trained to prevent undesirable outcomes in decision-making processes. This training includes diversifying data sets, regularly reviewing faulty algorithms, and encouraging transparency in algorithmic decision-making. Additionally, transparency and understandability are critical to building trust and accountability when integrating with AI. Stakeholders need to understand how AI algorithms work and the factors that influence their decisions to ensure ethical use and mitigate transparency concerns.

Overall, prioritizing ethical considerations when integrating AI is necessary to support the principles of privacy, fairness, transparency, and responsible use of technology. By following ethical standards and practices, organizations can increase trust, reduce risk, and improve social well-being when implementing AI-integrated management information systems.

CONCLUSION

Information is data about objects and phenomena of the environment that reduce the existing uncertainty, incompleteness of knowledge about them. Economic information is understood as a set of data reflecting the state or determining the change and development of the country's economy, all its links and elements[7]. This data can be recorded, transmitted, processed, stored and used in the process of planning, accounting, control, analysis at all levels of management. Information resources can be defined as a set of accumulated information recorded on tangible media in any form that ensures its transmission in time and space to solve scientific, industrial, managerial and other problems. Informatization is the saturation of all spheres of life and activity with increasing flows of information and their management using information technologies and telecommunication systems. Any system of management of an economic object corresponds to its own economic information system. The modern level of informatization of society predetermines the use of the latest technical, technological, software tools in the information systems of economic objects[8]. An automated information system is a complex that includes computer and communication equipment, software, linguistic tools, information resources, and system personnel, and provides support for a dynamic information model of some part of the real world to meet the information needs of users.

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